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COMMUNITY FINDING IN DYNAMIC NETWORKS USING A GENETIC ALGORITHM IMPROVED VIA A HYBRID IMMIGRANTS SCHEME

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ABSTRACT

Due to the temporal nature of real-world networks, the interest in community detection problems on dynamic networks have experienced an increasing attention over the last years. Genetic Algorithms, and other bio-inspired methods, have been successfully applied to tackle the community finding problem in static networks. However, few research works have been done related to the improvement of these algorithms for temporal or dynamic domains. This paper is focused on the design, implementation, and empirical analysis of a new Genetic Algorithm based on a *hybrid-immigrants scheme*, whose main goal is to improve the algorithm convergence when it is applied to identify communities on dynamic networks.

Keywords Dynamic community finding; Genetic algorithms; Graph computing; Network analysis

1 Introduction

Community detection is a highly relevant problem when it is applied to disciplines such as sociology, biology, marketing, or computer science, among others. A community can be defined as a set of nodes, whose interactions between the nodes, belonging to this set, are stronger than the interactions to the rest of nodes that belong to other communities. There are two basic approaches to this problem, the first one (named non-overlapping) considers that one node only can belong to a single community [1]. The second one, (named overlapping) allows each node to belong to several communities at time[2].

In recent years, motivated by the temporal nature of real-world networks such as social networks or mobile communications, new methods and algorithms have been proposed which can handle networks that evolve in time. The communities found by these algorithms are called *dynamic communities*. The evolution of a graph is usually modeled using a sequence of snapshots, where each snapshot represents the graph at a given point in time. A dynamic community can be modeled in two different ways[3]. The first one is a sequence of static communities, where there is a set of subgraphs representing the communities detected for each snapshot. On the other hand, in the second model, each dynamic community is represented as an initial static community and a sequence of modifications over time.

Four main approaches have been used in the literature to detect dynamic communities[3]: The first approach detects static communities for each snapshot independently and then match communities between consecutive snapshots[4]. The second approach processes all the sequence of snapshots simultaneously, a single community detection algorithm is applied once creating a set of communities which contains nodes from different snapshots[5]. The third approach

detects the static communities on the first snapshot, then the remaining snapshots are processed following a chronological order, and using the communities detected at the previous snapshot to identify the communities at current snapshot[6]. Finally, the fourth approach finds the static communities in the first snapshot, after that, in an iterative process and following a chronological order, the communities detected are updated using only the modifications of the network between consecutive snapshots[7].

Genetic Algorithms (GAs) are a stochastic meta-heuristic inspired in the biological principles of Darwinian theory of evolution and Mendel’s genetics. GAs have been used to detect both static[8, 9] and dynamic communities[4]. Many techniques have been developed to adapt GAs to dynamic environments so when a change occurs, if the new problem is similar to the previous one, the knowledge acquired for the previous solutions can be used to solve the new ones in order to decrease the computational effort. Some of these techniques are *hypermutation*[10] (increase the mutation rate of the population when a change occurs in the environment), *memory schemes*[11] (maintain a memory of individuals during all the GA execution, and when a change occurs, to use this memory to influence the actual population) or *immigrants*[5] (insert new individuals into the population when a change occurs in order to improve the population’s diversity). These techniques seem to work well together with the dynamic community detection approaches previously mentioned. For example, Yang and Tinós [12] introduced a new algorithm based on the *immigrants scheme* that aims to reduce the convergence time of GAs when applied to solve problems in dynamic environments.

However, few research works are focused on the application of these approaches to find communities into a temporal or dynamic network. In particular, for detecting dynamic communities, Keehyung et al.[5] presented a Multi-objective GA that uses different immigrants schemes. This algorithm follows the second approach, processing all the sequence of snapshots simultaneously, generating the same set of communities for all the snapshots in the network. Immigrants are inserted into the population for each generation of the algorithm, and the algorithm has 20 generations to adapt after each change.

Our paper presents a new algorithm for community finding on dynamic networks based on the third approach previously mentioned, instead of following the second approach proposed in Keehyung et al. [5]. Therefore, the new GA proposed generates a different set of communities for each snapshot of the network. Instead of inserting immigrants in the population at each generation, the proposed algorithm inserts immigrants only into the initial population of each GA trying to reduce the convergence time. In addition, the main contribution of these algorithms is that they keep the information of the changes in communities overtime. Finally, an empirical analysis of the new GA based on a immigrants scheme is carried out to evaluate the achieved improvements.

The rest of the paper is structured as follows: Section 2 describes the dynamic community detection problem. Section 3 presents the procedure followed to test the algorithm and discusses the experimental results. Finally, the last section draws some conclusions and the future research lines of work.

2 Proposed algorithm

2.1 Problem formulation

Let $DN = \{G^t | \forall t \in 0..n\}$ be a dynamic network with n snapshots, each one modeled as a graph G^t . The goal of the algorithm is to find a dynamic community identification $C_{dynamic}$. Which is a sequence of partitions P^t , one for each $G^t \in DN$, where the components in each P^t have more interactions inside them than between them. Components in the same P^t do not overlap, in other words, the intersection between them is empty.

2.2 Genetic algorithm and immigrants scheme

The proposed algorithm uses an immigrants scheme that extends a standard GA to detect dynamic communities for each snapshot (G^t) on the dynamic network (DN). As shown in 1 (lines 2 to 12), in the first snapshot (G^0), the algorithm works in the same way as the standard GA. However, for the rest of the snapshots ($\{G^t | t > 0\}$), instead of evolving a new random population, the algorithm evolves a population composed of a mixture of random individuals, and individuals from the previous snapshot’s population.

Each individual in the population represents one possible partition(P^t) of the current snapshot(G^t) using the Locus-based adjacency representation [13]. According to this encoding, each individual of the initial random population (line 6) is generated by filling each position in the chromosome with a random neighbor, in G^t , of the node that the gen codifies. On the other hand, for generating the individuals of the initial immigrant population related to the snapshots after G^0 , the *Immigrants Selection* and *Repair* functions are applied to pass individuals between populations (line 8). The first function (line 15) selects the N-best individuals from the old population that pass to the new one, if the new population is not full, as many individuals are randomly chosen and added as needed (line 14). The second function

Algorithm 1 GA for detecting dynamic communities

```

1: function DYNAMICCOMMUNITIESGA( $DN$ )
2:    $C_{dynamic} \leftarrow \emptyset$ 
3:    $C_{last} \leftarrow null$ 
4:   for all  $G^t \in DN$  do
5:     if  $t = 0 \vee standardGA$  then
6:        $P_{initial} \leftarrow makeRandomPopulation(G^t, popSize)$ 
7:     else
8:        $P_{initial} \leftarrow makeImmigrantPopulation(C_{last}, G^t, popSize, randomRate)$ 
9:      $C_{actual} \leftarrow elitistGA(P_{initial}, G^t, elitism, crxRate, mutateRate, nGenerations)$ 
10:     $C_{last} \leftarrow C_{actual}$ 
11:     $C_{dynamic} \leftarrow C_{dynamic} \cup C_{actual}$ 
12:  return  $C_{dynamic}$ 
13: function MAKEIMMIGRANTPOPULATION( $C_{last}, G^t, popSize, randomRate$ )
14:   $P_{random} \leftarrow makeRandomPopulation(G^t, popSize * randomRate)$ 
15:   $P_{elite} \leftarrow selectBest(C_{last}, popSize * (1 - randomRate))$ 
16:  for all  $individual \in P_{elite}$  do
17:     $individual \leftarrow repair(individual, G^t)$ 
18:  return  $P_{elite} \cup P_{random}$ 
19: function REPAIR( $individual, G^t$ )
20:  for all  $i \in [1, size(individual)]$  do
21:    if  $individual[i] \notin neighbors(i, G^t)$  then
22:       $individual[i] \leftarrow selectRandom(neighbors(i, G^t))$ 
23:  return  $individual$ 

```

(line 16 to 17) repairs the individuals, from the old population, that represent invalid solutions in the new population. This function (lines 20 to 22) checks if a gen inside an individual's chromosome points to a node that no longer is connected to the node with the same id as the gen position. When this occurs the gen value is changed to the id of a random neighbor of the node that the gen codifies.

Once the initial population (random or immigrant) has been created, it evolves using an elitist genetic algorithm (line 9) with the next functions: *Uniform Crossover*, *Roulette wheel selection*, *modularity* [1] as *Fitness function* and for *Mutation* a function that randomly selects a series of gens, and change them with a random neighbor of the corresponding node.

3 Experimental study

To study the effectiveness of our approach we have compared it against a standard GA without immigrants measuring the number of generations that both need to reach the optimum modularity value. We have used a synthetic benchmarks generator[14] that allows to create dynamic networks that evolve in a periodic manner, more specifically, a dynamic network with 100 snapshots, 512 nodes, 17205 edges and a periodicity of 100 time steps have been created.

The degree of change between snapshots in the generated network is not homogeneous. For measuring this degree we have calculated the percentage of neighbors of each node that change between consecutive snapshots. In order to have datasets with different degree of change we have selected three sets of 10 consecutive snapshots from the 100 snapshots of the dynamic network. Fig. 1 shows the median percentage of neighbors that change for each snapshot in the datasets. All the experimentation will be done over this three sets.

The set-up of the GA which has been used during the experimentation phase is: crossover rate 0.8, mutation rate 0.2 and elite reproduction 10% of the population size. The population size is 300 and the *stop condition* is fulfilled when the number of generations reach 120. The different parameters of the algorithm have been tuned up experimentally.

In order to select the optimal mixture of random and previous individuals for the initial population (parameter *randomRate* in the line 9 of 1), we have tested the next random-elite ratios: 0%-100%, 20%-80%, 40%-60%, 60%-40%, 80%-20% and 100%-0%, being the last one the standard GA without immigrants. Each experiment has been performed 10 times. To measure the efficiency of the technique, we compare the median number of generations that the algorithm takes to reach the highest fitness value using the different immigrants rates. Results can be seen in the Fig. 2.

Analyzing these results, we can conclude that convergence speed improves if a percentage of individuals from the previous execution of the GA passes to the next snapshot and the variation between snapshots is low. In addition, comparing these results (Fig. 2), and the degree of change shown in Fig. 1, we can draw a parallelism between the results obtained for each snapshot of the different datasets. For example looking at the *middle* dataset, in snapshots 3, 4 and 5, as the degree of change decreases the efficiency of the immigrants scheme improves. We can see the opposite effect if we check snapshots 6, 7 and 8 of the same dataset. An extreme example can be seen between snapshots 8

In blue bars, median of the percentage of neighbors of a node that change between consecutive time steps. Orange horizontal line shows the median for all values.

Figure 1: Percentage of neighbors that change for each snapshot in the datasets.

The X axis contains each snapshot. The Y axis contains the median number of generations needed to achieve the optimum fitness value. Each bar represents a different ratio of random individuals present in the initial population of that generation. The blue bar 100% uses a completely new random population (the standard GA). The yellow one uses the entire population of the last generation

Figure 2: Result of applying different immigrants rates for each dataset.

and 9. At the beginning of the snapshot 8 we have a degree of change over 80%, which makes the immigrants scheme nearly as good as the standard GA. On the other side, at the beginning of snapshot 9, we have a degree of change of 0% making the immigrants scheme very effective. This behavior can be explained examining the *repair* operator. Our operator randomizes the parts of an individual that change between snapshots. When a big part of an individual changes between snapshots the operator is unable to reuse the knowledge generated in the previous snapshot and it transforms the initial population into a random population even though individuals from the previous snapshot are present. Therefore, we have not found a clear random-elite ratio to improve the overall performance. However, our results suggest that a reasonable choice could be in the range 0-20.

4 Conclusions and future work

This paper presents a new evolutionary approach based on a GA using an immigrant scheme to detect communities on dynamic networks. This approach executes a GA to identify the communities belonging to each snapshot of the network. In order to improve the convergence speed, a combination of the best individuals from the previous execution of the GA, and random individuals, is used as the initial population of the next execution of GA. Experiments on synthetic datasets show that this approach is effective in networks where the degree of change is low. Taking into account the experimental results, it can be concluded that the repair operator used to keep individuals along generations is too basic and it fails when the change between consecutive snapshots is high. Future research will be focused on the design of new repair operators that could better transfer information between snapshots despite the degree of change between them.

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